

Questionnaire for Czech high school physics teachers

This questionnaire aims on gathering insights from physics teachers regarding the teaching of quantum physics at high schools. We are also interested in your opinion on incorporating topics related to quantum technologies into physics education. Your perspective is valuable to us even if you do not teach quantum physics currently. When completing the questionnaire, please keep in mind:

- If you teach physics at multiple schools or at distinct study programs within one school, please relate your answers to one of them.
- Within the questionnaire, we distinguish between questions concerning teaching of the entire topic physics of microcosm (involving topics such as nuclear physics, particle physics, atomic physics) and questions specifically focused on quantum physics (including topics such as quantum mechanical model of atom, wave-particle duality, uncertainty principle, etc.).

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The following questions concern regular physics lessons:

1) Do you get on with dedicating to topics from physics of microcosm in your common physics lessons (e.g. nuclear physics, particle physics, atomic physics, quantum physics)? (*Single choice*)

- a) Yes, normally I dedicate to physics of microcosm in my classes. (→ 1A)
- b) No, but I used to. (→ 1B)
- c) No, but I am planning to. (→ 1B)
- d) No and I am not planning to. (→ 1B)

1A) Please, estimate how many lessons you usually dedicate to physics of microcosm (if you address the topic in several years, estimate the total sum over the years): (*Single choice*) (→ 2)

- a) 1–2 lessons
- b) 3–6 lessons
- c) 7–10 lessons
- d) 11–20 lessons
- e) More than 20 lessons

2) Do you dedicate to quantum physics specifically in your common physics lessons? (*Single choice*)

- a) Yes, normally I dedicate to quantum physics in my lessons. (→ 3)
- b) No, but I used to. (→ 2B)
- c) No, but I am planning to. (→ 2B)
- d) No and I am not planning to. (→ 2B)

3) Please, estimate how many lessons you usually dedicate to quantum physics specifically (i.e. not to the entire module Physics of microcosm): If you address the topic in several years, estimate the total sum over the years: (*Single choice*) (→ 4)

- a) 1–2 lessons
- b) 3–4 lessons
- c) 5–6 lessons
- d) 7–8 lessons
- e) 9–10 lessons
- f) More than 10 lessons

4) What is the most important goal for you in teaching quantum physics? (→ 4A)

4A) What do you consider as the basics principles and concepts of quantum physics? (→ 5)

5) What forms or activities do you use in your teaching of quantum physics? (→ 6)

- a) Lecturing
- b) Class discussion
- c) Group work
- d) Individual work
- e) Calculations
- f) Working with text, textbooks
- g) Demonstration experiments
- h) Student experiments
- i) Lab work
- j) Working with applets, computer simulations and visualizations
- k) Other

6) Which quantum physics topics do you talk about with students? (→ 7)

- a) Philosophical aspects and history of quantum physics
- b) Different behaviour of objects in microcosm (wave-particle duality, particle behaviour of light, ...)
- c) Probabilistic description of a quantum state (e.g. wave function, probability density, ...)
- d) Superposition
- e) Statistical character of measurement in quantum physics
- f) Uncertainty relations
- g) Entanglement
- h) Quantization (e.g. of energy in atoms, connection with atomic spectra)
- i) Double slit experiment
- j) Photoelectric effect
- k) Compton effect
- l) Hydrogen atom, atomic orbitals, quantum mechanical atomic model
- m) Indistinguishability, Pauli exclusion principle, periodic table of elements
- n) Tunnelling
- o) Potential well
- p) Spin
- q) Stern-Gerlach experiment
- r) LASER
- s) LED, semiconductors
- t) Other

7) What materials do you use in your quantum physics teaching? (→ 7A)

- a) Textbook
- b) Web pages
- c) Videos
- d) Interactive visualizations, applets, simulations
- e) Other

7A) Please, could you specify which concrete sources and materials you use: (→ 7B)

7B) How should the teaching materials look like, so that you would appreciate them the most for your quantum physics teaching? (→ 7C)

- a) Comprehensive study text appropriate to the high school level
- b) Several standalone short texts on different quantum physics topics
- c) Inspiration for activities with students
- d) Inspiration of demonstration experiments

- e) Interactive simulations, applets, visualizations
- f) Instructive videos
- g) Other

7C) Here you can describe in more details what materials you would appreciate the most for your quantum physics teaching: (→ 8)

1B) For what main reasons do you not dedicate to physics of microcosm in your common lessons? (→ 2D)

2A) For what main reasons do you not dedicate to quantum physics in your common lessons? (→ 2B)

2B) Please, state what other topics you talk about with students in your teaching of physics of microcosm: (→ 2C)

2C) What do you consider to be the basics principles and concepts of quantum physics? (→ 2D)

2D) If you were supposed to teach quantum physics, would you know where to find suitable materials for your teaching? (→ 2E)

- a) Yes, I would know where to find suitable materials.
- b) I am not sure.

2E) Please, could you specify the concrete materials and sources you would use: (→ 8)

The following questions concern your opinion on teaching quantum physics:

8) Do you think that high school students should be introduced to the basic principles of quantum physics? (*Single choice*)

- a) Yes, all students in regular physics lessons. (→ 8A)
- b) Yes, but only chosen students (e.g. in optional seminars, etc.). (→ 8B)
- c) No, I do not think that high school students should be introduced to this topic. (→ 8C)

8A) Please, specify why you think that all students should be introduced to the basic principles of quantum physic: (→ 9)

8B) Please, specify why you think that only chosen students should be introduced to the basic principles of quantum physic (e.g.in optional seminars): (→ 9)

8C) Please, specify why you think that students should not be introduced to the basic principles of quantum physic: (→ 9)

9) Do you think that quantum physics is more attractive for students, comparing to other physic topics (e.g. mechanics, electricity and magnetism, optics, thermodynamics, ...)? (→ 9) (*Likert scale*)

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

The following questions concern optional physics seminars:

10) Do you teach, or have you taught in past three years, the optional physics seminar? (*Single choice*)

- a) Yes (→ 11)
- b) No (→ 11)

11) What is the seminar aimed at? (*Single choice*) (→ 12)

- a) The seminar is aimed at the maturita exam revision only.
- b) The seminar is aimed at broadening topics, not only at the maturita exam revision.

12) Do you dedicate to quantum physics in the seminar? (*Single choice*)

- a) Yes, normally I dedicate to quantum physics in the seminar. (→ 13)

- b) No, but I used to. (→ 12A)
- c) No, but I am planning to. (→ 12A)
- d) No and I am not planning to. (→ 12A)

13) Please, estimate how many lessons you usually dedicate to quantum physics in the seminar: (*Single choice*) (→ 14)

- a) 1–2 lessons
- b) 3–4 lessons
- c) 5–6 lessons
- d) 7–8 lessons
- e) 9–10 lessons
- f) More than 10 lessons

14) Which quantum physics topics do you talk about with students in the seminar? (→ I1)

- a) Philosophical aspects and history of quantum physics
- b) Different behaviour of objects in microcosm (wave-particle duality, particle behaviour of light, ...)
- c) Probabilistic description of a quantum state (e.g. wave function, probability density, ...)
- d) Superposition
- e) Statistical character of measurement in quantum physics
- f) Uncertainty relations
- g) Entanglement
- h) Quantization (e.g. of energy in atoms, connection with atomic spectra)
- i) Double slit experiment
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- l) Hydrogen atom, atomic orbitals, quantum mechanical atomic model
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- q) Stern-Gerlach experiment
- r) LASER
- s) LED, semiconductors
- t) Other

12A) For what main reasons do you not dedicate to quantum physics in the seminar?

Final information

At the close, please, fill in the information about the region, type of your school, and your teaching practice. Your responses are entirely anonymous, this information will be used for the demographical mapping of the respondents only.

I1) Please, choose the type of your school (which you related your responses to): (*Multiple choice*)

- a) Gymnasium (→ I2)
- b) Other high school (→ I1A)

I1A) Is quantum physics a part of your school's curriculum? (*Single choice*) (→ I2)

- a) Yes
- b) No

c) Other

I2) Please, choose the region of your school: (→ I3)

a) (The List of 14 regions in the Czech Republic)

I3) Please, choose your length of your teaching experience: (*Single choice*) (→ I4)

a) 0–2 years

b) 3–5 years

c) 6–10 years

d) 11–20 years

e) 21–30 years

f) 31 or more years

I4) Please, choose what is your professional background: (→ I5)

a) I have completed a university program in Physics Education.

b) I have completed a university program in other pedagogical field than Physics Education.

c) I have completed a university program in Physics or other related domain.

d) Other

I5) Quantum physics is one of my favourite subjects. (→ I6) (*Likert scale*)

• Strongly agree • Agree • Disagree • Strongly disagree

I6) Here you can comment on any topic regarding quantum physics teaching: (→ I7)